

LEarning and action alliances for NexuS Environments
in an uncertain future

LENSES

WP9

D9.2 Visual identity and project identity material

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Project partners

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Project Website:

www.lenses-prima.eu

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GA n° [2041] [LENSES] [Call 2020 Section 1 Nexus IA]

LENSES Visual identity and project identity material

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Executive Summary

This document describes the objectives, structure, and look and feel of the project visual identity and templates. The visual identity is an essential means for the LENSES project to reach its objectives concerning communication, as well as strengthening the project's identity and positioning LENSES as a strong brand.

This includes various components (the project logo, the key visual, the color palette) which will constitute the base to develop a wide range of dissemination and communication tools, e.g. a series of general templates and master documents, the project website, project related platform (e.g. LAA platform and the catalogue on Nature Based Solutions), roll-ups, brochure and poster for a general overview of the project.

All of these tools are essential to reach project objectives in regards to communication, including strengthening the project's identity, raising awareness and disseminating project developments to key stakeholders and external actors.

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LENSES visual identity and project identity material

Introduction

LENSES aspires to create a **Water-Ecosystem-Food (WEF) Nexus narrative and Call to Action in the framework of a changing climate**. The core message of this narrative is the **paradigm shift from Nexus Thinking to Resilient Nexus Doing** for strengthening the resilience of socio-ecological systems. To this end, the project will reach out to the general public with visual tools to create awareness on the WEF Nexus, i.e. the interactions among **four domains** (water allocation, ecosystem services, food production, climate adaptation - in a cross-cutting manner) and to inform on the benefits and positive impact of adopting comprehensive nexus management strategies, e.g. potential to create new socio-economic opportunities.

In order to maximise the project impact, a dedicated LENSES Dissemination and Communication strategy (D&C strategy, D9.1) was produced in June 2021 (M2), and has been improved and updated up to October 2022 (M18), in a continuous learning-by-doing process. The LENSES D&C strategy aims to publicize concrete results and positive feedback loops created by the participatory development and application of LENSES principles by the Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) in the pilots. These results will be used to further advertise the potential of LENSES in informing and shaping policy, helping to break down silos among the four domains and overcome Nexus 'inertia'. The D&C strategy defines objectives, targeted audiences, key messages, communication channels, action plan and KPIs. At the local pilot level, it aims to create Nexus awareness and promote the growth and work of LAAs. By providing visibility to LAA actions, for example through the use of digital and social media, it will provide an added incentive for partners to participate, as well as inspire other LAAs across pilot areas.

In order to support the achievement of the objectives defined within the LENSES D&C strategy, a dedicated **visual identity** has been created for the LENSES project. It includes various components (the project logo, the key visual, the color palette) which will constitute the base to develop a wide range of dissemination and communication tools, e.g. a series of general templates and master documents, the project website, project related platform (e.g. LAA platform and the catalogue on Nature Based Solutions), roll-ups, brochure and poster for a general overview of the project. This visual identity has been designed to transport values such as simplicity, progress and community. By developing a professional joint image and appearance together with the clear and consistent design of the LENSES project, a solid and future-oriented basis for further dissemination and exploitation activities has been set.

This document reflects the final version of the LENSES visual identity. It includes all project identity materials developed from the LENSES starting date (01 May 2021) until October 2022 (M18).

1. Key elements of LENSES visual identity

1.1 Objectives

The visual identity created for the LENSES project aims to facilitate the implementation of all communication and dissemination activities foreseen within the project in order to ensure an effective transfer of project results and of know-how to several target audiences. Furthermore, it provides a solid basis to develop professionally crafted project identity materials facilitating an optimal dissemination and exploitation of the project's results.

A series of project identity materials - respecting LENSES visual identity- has been created, and regularly updated, throughout the project lifespan. These include a project logo, several communication products (e.g. general project brochure, PPT and poster) and templates, as well as the project website, with the core aim to inform the different stakeholders and the wider public about the project.

The objective of the LENSES visual identity and visual identity material is to increase the public visibility of the project and subsequently its outcomes, as well as facilitate the overall project goal to create a WEF Nexus narrative and Call to Action.

1.2 Acknowledgement of EU funding

All LENSES visual identity products and templates (e.g. brochure, poster, PPT) will comply with the GA requirements, and respectively with art. 38.1.2 Information on PRIMA funding — Obligation and right to use the PRIMA logo and the EU emblem; and art. 29.4 Information on PRIMA funding — Obligation and right to use the PRIMA logo and the EU emblem. Therefore, unless the PRIMA Foundation requests or agrees otherwise or it is impossible, any visual identity materials (in any form, including electronic) will:

- (a) display the PRIMA logo, and
- (b) display the EU emblem, and
- (c) include the following text: "This project is part of the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union. GA n° [2041] [LENSES] [Call 2020 Section 1 Nexus IA]".

When displayed together with another logo, the PRIMA logo and the EU emblem will have appropriate prominence.

Furthermore, all LENSES visual identity materials will include, according to Art. 29.5 Disclaimer excluding the PRIMA Foundation responsibility of the GA, the following sentence: "This publication reflects only the author's view and the PRIMA Foundation is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains".

2. Description of the LENSES visual identity

A project visual identity has been created as the essential flagship of the LENSES project with the main goal of establishing and conveying a coherent image and brand recognition leading to an optimal presentation and recognition of the project.

The brand identity uses a set of graphic elements to easily identify the LENSES Project, e.g. contribute to identifying LENSES D&C activities, such as publications and all kinds of writings as well as visual communication about on-going and completed research activities. This section gives an overview and a brief description of how to apply LENSES visual identity and design elements to LENSES products and materials.

2.1 Key Visual

A key visual is an image motive that is used in a brand presence in order to enhance the brand recognition. For the LENSES brand, overlapping intersected waves have been chosen. The overlapping waves are symbolizing the dynamic interaction among the four domains (water allocation, ecosystem services, food production, climate adaptation) of the Nexus as well as the cross-cutting approach uses to look at them in the context of LENSES. Consequently, the overlapping intersected waves have been chosen to operate as key visual and are recurrently adopted throughout the whole visual identity.

The brand recognition is ensured as the intersected waves are coherently reused on the website and all other communication and dissemination products. Thanks to the dynamics of the intersected waves, flexibility, a future-orientated mindset as well as a striving for revolutionary solutions are being conveyed. The design implies the discovery of pioneering and innovative ideas, which present and future generations will benefit from.

Figure 1: LENSES Key visual. Three versions of the intersected waves used. The overlapping waves are symbolizing the dynamic interaction among the four domains (water allocation, ecosystem services, food production, climate adaptation) of the Nexus as well as the cross-cutting approach uses to look at them in the context of LENSES.

The intersected waves, representing the four domains of the Nexus, have been colored in four colors (blue, green, yellow and white, representing respectively the Water, Ecosystems, Food and Climate domains – Fig.1, parts “a” and “b”) or by using colored related textures (Fig.1, part “c”).

2.2 LENSES logo

Logo, brand and image make people recognize a project: “a strong **brand** has to do with every project aspect and project relationship with its target groups”.¹

Figure 2: LENSES project logo

A project logo (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**) was designed to make the LENSES project easily recognizable. The LENSES logo can be easily:

1. Recognized;
2. Reduced or enlarged (size flexibility);
3. Applied to different media tools (printouts, animation, web-design, ...);
4. Reproduced by needlework for preparing promotional items; and
5. Printed both in color and in black and white only.

The logo of the project has been used in all internal and external documents that the project produces to communicate its activities and results.

¹Pinnacle, *Project Communication Guide*, INTERREG VIC Programme, April 2012, p. 11.

2.3 Color palette

All project templates and materials use a distinctive custom color palette, which includes the four colors reported in Table 1.

Table 1: The colours of LENSES project

Colours	R	G	B
	251	187	56
	24	120	174
	79	145	33
	255	255	255

The RGB color palette can be customized manually in MS Word.

2.4 Typeface

All templates and materials have been created with the defined typefaces. The use of one font type for all deliverables makes the template distinctive, increases its originality and helps to promote a uniform template image, a fact that increases the dissemination quality.

For the corporate use of text for the LENSES project, the typeface family “Calibri fonts” has been chosen. Calibri fonts, which are a humanist sans serif typeface, were designed by Lucas de Groot. Calibri fonts features subtly rounded stems and corners that are visible at larger sizes.

3. LENSES visual identity material

In order to facilitate project partners in their communication and dissemination activities and to implement them by accomplishing all LENSES visibility rules described in Chapters 1 and 2 of this document, a series of templates for C&D materials and tools have been prepared and made available to all partners, in editable format, in the folder “Templates” of the “[Partner area](#)” present on the project’s website. The “Partner area” can be accessed upon registration.

This chapter reports a few examples of LENSES communication and dissemination templates that shall be used as a basis to prepare customised materials for specific audiences that the partners want to approach. Project partners are responsible to adapt these templates for being used both in English and in local languages.

3.1 Power Point templates

Two LENSES Power Point (PPT) templates have been set up to support the visual identification of the project during public events, such as conferences, speeches, meetings and in general presenting research results, both inside and outside the project, as well as for the activities involving project stakeholders for internal and external presentations. A preliminary version of LENSES Power Point template, whose key elements are shown in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.a**, was shared among all project partners already ahead of the project’s kick-off meeting. Thereafter, an enhanced version of the PPT template, slightly different from the first one, has been created in January 2022 and is represented in **Figure 3b**. The enhanced version of the PPT template presents homogeneous graphic elements used in all LENSES communication materials and tools (general poster, brochure, etc...) – see Chapter 4 of this document.

In addition to the PPT template, a general PPT to present the project has been prepared to support communication to the general public (see session 4.2 of this document). This presentation has been made available to the general public in the “Outcomes” web section (<https://www.lenses-prima.eu/outcomes/communication-and-dissemination/>)

Figure 3: LENSES PPT preliminary (a) and advanced (b) templates. Both of them include a first slide including space for title, speaker(s) name and partner institution logo (top-left); a basic slide to be used as a layout for the body of the presentation (top-right); a slide including all project partners (bottom-left); and one slide for closure, including the logo of the institution and the contact(s) of the speaker(s) (bottom-right).

3.2 MS Word template

For the needs of the production and writing of the official project's documents, such as project deliverables (63 in total, among draft and final versions, public and confidential), an MS Word template has been developed. The purpose of such a template is to have a consistent and recognizable layout for all project's documents produced for an internal documentation and workflow, as well as for deliverables addressed to the project donor. The MS Word template includes all visual settings developed for the LENSES project.

The cover page of the MS Word template (Figure 4 **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**, right) displays the key visual, the project's logo and the title of the project in a prominent position, the number and title of the document, the working package in which the document has been developed and its main author(s). At the bottom of the page all the logos of the project partners and the information related to acknowledgement of EU funding are clearly displayed.

The second page of the MS Word template includes only information about its graphic designers.

The third page of the MS Word template contains a table with key information related to both the project and the document (e.g. Project no, acronym and title; authors, title, expected due date and actual date of submission of the deliverable) and, at the bottom of the page, a further table with the document history. The following page includes the tables of content and figures.

The closing page of the MS word template (Figure 4, left) contains, at the bottom, the disclaimer that excludes the responsibility of the PRIMA Foundation for any use that may be made of the information contained in any deliverable as required by Grant Agreement Article 29.5.

All the above-mentioned pages of the template remain static, do not change and contain only the information referred above. The template constituting the body of the document, contains at its footer both the PRIMA logo and the EU emblem, as well as the sentence related to the funding source acknowledgement and the number of the Grant Agreement. The header of this page includes the project logo (left side), the title of the document (in the middle) and the logo of the partner institution responsible for it (right side).

The MS word template uses only the Calibri fonts, which makes the template distinctive, increases its originality and helps to promote a uniform template image, a fact that increases the dissemination quality.

The standard template formatting is as follows:

Margins: 2 cm (left, right, up, down)

Line spacing: multiple, 1,15 pt.

Document body (Normal): Calibri 11, Paragraph: 6pt after **Heading 1:** Calibri Bold 22, Blue color

Heading 2: Calibri Bold 20, Green color **Heading3:** Calibri Bold 18, Yellow color

It must be noted that the MS word template can be updated during the course of the project, but colors and fonts will remain the same.

Figure 4: LENSES MS Word template

3.3 Scientific poster template

A poster template to support the presentation of the project, specific project activities or topics to a scientific audience has been prepared.

Figure 5: LENSES Poster template

The poster template includes, in its top-left corner, the logo of the LENSES project, and in its bottom frame all graphic elements characterizing both the project (i.e. LENSES visual identity elements) and the PRIMA Foundation. Among the latest, the poster template includes: the PRIMA logo (bottom-left), the EU emblem (bottom-right), and the sentence related to the funding source including the number of the Grant Agreement.

3.4 Roll-up template

Figure 6: LENSES roll-up template

A template for project roll-up was prepared with the aim to support the presentation of the project, or specific project activities in public meetings and workshops (Figure 6).

The roll-up template includes, in its left frame, the logos of all partners in the consortium.

In the bottom frame of the roll up includes, just above the intersected waves, the official project e-mail and the address of the project website, together with the names of the main social LENSES accounts (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn).

All the above-described components were included as not editable elements, while two columns (the central and the right-side column) include text and images that can be edited to meet specific requirements of partners (e.g. local language text) or different purposes of use.

4. Communication materials and tools

LENSES has a strong focus on the local dimension. Consequently, most communication activities shall be necessarily tailored on the specific needs of the people involved in pilot activities, which largely vary among different regions. For this reason, the partners have decided to prepare common communication tools and materials (i.e., general materials) that can be easily adapted to specific needs and occasions, with the aim to facilitate the recognition of the project. Therefore, a number of common communication products, including all graphic elements characterizing both the project (LENSES visual identity elements) and the PRIMA Foundation (e.g. the PRIMA logo, the EU emblem, the sentence related to the funding source and the number of the Grant Agreement) have been designed and made available for all partners. Finalized communication tools have been shared through the LENSES website (see “Communication and Dissemination Tools” in the [Outcomes](#) web section) as well as via social media, ready to be used. On the other hand, the same communication and dissemination tools have been made available for all partners, in editable format, in the dedicated “[Partner area](#)” accessible upon registration. Communication products have been used by all partners in English or translated into local languages depending on the type of target audience. Next sections provide a detailed description of all the general LENSES communication and dissemination materials, together with information on where to view or download them.

4.1 LENSES brochure

The project brochure is a two-page document. Each page constitutes one side of the brochure and is divided in three parts, so that when the brochure is closed each of these three parts constitute a “sub-page” of the brochure.

The external side of the brochure (Figure 5 top), in its right side, that is the opening page of the brochure, brings together all graphic elements characterizing both the project and the donors: the project logo is on the top-left of the opening page, while on the top-right of the same page is the logo of the lead partner (CREA). The project title is on the central part of the opening page, together with the final part of the LENSES key visual element, the intersected waves, that is drawn across the entire external side of the brochure. On the bottom right part of the opening page are both the PRIMA logo and the EU emblem, together with the sentence related to the funding source and the number of the Grant Agreement. On the external side of the brochure, in its left side, all details about the composition of the *Consortium* are reported. In particular, the list of all project partners including, per each partner, the logo and the name of the Institution, the name and the contacts of the team leader. The central parts of the external side of the brochure includes, in its top, the general contacts of the project (email address) and the project website. In its central part it includes the name of the LENSES accounts on the main social channels (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn), and key visual elements of the project. The footer includes the disclaimer that excludes the responsibility of the PRIMA Foundation for any use that may be made of the information contained the brochure, as required by Article 29.5 of the Grant Agreement.

In its second page, which constitutes the internal side of the brochure (Figure 5 bottom), the document includes a general overview of the project: it explains the 4 Nexus domains and the 9 specific project

objectives. Furthermore, it offers a map to locate the 7 pilot areas and explains the main types of stakeholders addressed by the project (i.e. public, private, multilateral). Figure 7 is a copy of the LENSES brochure.

Figure 7: LENSES general brochure. On the top part, the external side of the brochure. On the bottom part, the internal side of the brochure.

4.2 LENSES presentation

LENSES

LEarning and action alliances for NexuS EnvironmentS

in an uncertain future

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4 NEXUS DOMAINS

LENSES will enable multi-stakeholders communities to move from domain thinking to Nexus Thinking and Nexus Doing in very practical ways. It will enhance the understanding of the complex web of interactions affecting the nexus by using algorithms which link the different domains and run dynamic scenarios.

Vulnerabilities across the nexus domains will be reduced by harnessing ecosystem services and biodiversity through e.g. nature-based solutions.

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7 PILOT AREAS

All selected pilot areas represent typical Mediterranean conditions at the same time being very heterogeneous for their focus on conflicting water and land uses, food production chains, farmland, forest and natural ecosystems conservation activities, co-existence of agriculture, and other (e.g. tourism, industrial production, etc.) productive realms. Specific lessons from the pilots will be captured to capitalize in the future elsewhere in similar environments.

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8 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

LENSES follows a mixed methodology. On one hand, it is guided by hypothesis and the need for generalizable findings and broadly applicable methodologies and, on the other hand, by the need for a challenge-driven innovation approach. Here below, a list of LENSES key approaches.

- Participatory Approaches and Learning & Action Alliances (LAAs)
- Policy Recommendations
- Participatory System Dynamics Modelling (PSDM)
- Ecosystem Services Assessments
- Nexus-SDG co-evaluations
- Natural Resource Economics
- Nature-based Solutions
- Gender dimension

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MULTIPLE STAKEHOLDERS

LENSES supports a mutual-learning process in multi-actors communities among the pilots. This will help identify existing WEF challenges and conflicts in resource uses, assess the multi-dimensional implications of choices and policies and exploring pathways to implementing specific measures (e.g. nature-based solutions).

PUBLIC

- Public Authorities & Policy Makers
- National Universities & Research Institutes
- Asset Owners
- River Basin/ Water Management bodies
- Media & press (local, national, EU & Med)

PRIVATE

- Farmers - Cooperatives - NGOs & CSOs - Water Users Associations - Relevant Associations - Participants in LAAs & general public -

MULTILATERAL

- International Organisations & Processes
- International Financial Institutions & Donors
- Multinational Research Centers

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GA n° [2041] [LENSES] [Call 2020 Section 1 Nexus IA]

13 PROJECT PARTNERS

Center for Multicultural Research and Economics (CREM)

TESAF University of Pinar Department of Land, Environment, Agriculture and Forestry (Turkey)	ISSA Water Research Institute of the National Research Council (Italy)	EVIATION EVIATION S.A. (Italy)	agrisat AgriSat Iberia, S.L. (Spain)	ecoadapta EcoAdapta (Spain)	SWRI Soil and Water Resources Institute of the National Agricultural Organization "Mihail Kogalniceanu" (Romania)
TEC Technical University of Cluj-Napoca (Romania)	MIGAL Galileo Research Institute (Italy)	National Agricultural Research Center (Jordan)	DRAXIS Draxis Environmental S.A. (Greece)	International Agricultural Research and Training Center (Turkey)	Ea-Tek Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Zaragoza (Spain)

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Details

Duration: 01 May 2021 - 30 April 2024
Budget: 3.482.000,00
EU contribution: 2.998.000,00

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THANKS FOR YOUR ATTENTION!

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Figure 8: LENSES general PPT

4.3 LENSES poster

the LENSES project

LEarning and action alliances for Nexus Environments in an uncertain future
LENSES

Coordinated by **crea**

CONSORTIUM

The economic use of natural resources, such as water and land, in the Mediterranean region are constrained by resources limitations, climatic conditions and socio-economic stresses. The project *LEarning and action alliances for Nexus Environments in an uncertain future* (LENSES) aims to improve the understanding of WEF systems, to reveal their complexity, and to create innovative tools and strategies that help to manage their uncertainty, in relation to their dynamic evolution.

FROM NEXUS THINKING TO NEXUS DOING

Moving beyond the scientific Nexus understanding, LENSES aims to support the operationalization of the Nexus paradigm (from Nexus thinking to Nexus doing), therefore contributing to improve water allocation, enhance food security while preserving ecosystems and aiding climate change adaptation. LENSES integrates the concepts of sustainable Nexus management with a resilience-oriented approach, leading stakeholders in accepting uncertainty as integral part of management and decision-making processes.

4 NEXUS DOMAINS

LENSES will enable multi-stakeholders communities to move from domain thinking to Nexus Thinking and Nexus Doing in very practical ways. It will enhance the understanding of the complex web of interactions affecting the nexus by using algorithms which link the different domains and run dynamic scenarios. Vulnerabilities across the nexus domains will be reduced by harnessing ecosystem services and biodiversity through e.g. nature-based solutions.

MULTIPLE STAKEHOLDERS

LENSES will support a mutual-learning process in multi-actors communities among the pilots. This will help identify existing WEF challenges and conflicts in resource uses, assess the multi-dimensional implications of choices and policies and exploring pathways to implementing specific measures (e.g. nature-based solutions).

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- Public Authorities & Policy Makers
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PRIVATE

- Farmers - Cooperatives
- NGOs & CSOs
- Water Users Associations
- Relevant Associations
- Participants in LAAs & general public

MULTILATERAL

- International Organizations & Processes
- International Financial Institutions & Donors
- Multinational Research Centers

5 SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To identify Nexus Domain Objectives (DOs) & Nexus Resilience Qualities (NRQ) that facilitate the transition.
2. To activate Learning & Action Alliances (LAAs) to drive the Nexus dialogue.
3. To develop Participatory System Dynamics Models (PSDM) to support evidence-based policy design.
4. To co-design scenarios to test WEF Nexus resilience.
5. To carry out Ecosystem Services (ES) assessments to inform multi-objective policies and measures.
6. To assess and manage interdependencies between Nexus and SDGs.
7. To improve Natural Governance and align WEF policies toward Nexus management.
8. To build Nexus business cases using environmental and ecological economics.
9. To plan Nature-based Solutions (NBS) measures to co-achieve multiple DOs.

7 PILOT AREAS

All selected pilot areas represent typical Mediterranean conditions at the same time being very heterogeneous for their focus on conflicting water and land uses, food production chains, farmland, forest and natural ecosystems conservation activities, co-existence of agriculture, and other (e.g. tourism, industrial production, etc.) productive realms. Specific lessons from the pilots will be captured to capitalize in the future elsewhere in similar environments.

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- Gender dimension

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- Duration: 01 May 2021 - 30 April 2024
- Budget: 3.462.000,00
- EU co-financing: 2.488.000,00

Contacts

- Info: info.lenesa@crea.gov.it
- Website: www.lenesa-project.eu

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PRIMA IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AREA

This poster reflects only the author's view and the PRIMA Foundation is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This project is part of the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union. GA n° [2041] [LENSES] [Call 2020 Section 1 Nexus IA]

Following the poster template described in Session 3.3 of this document, a general poster including an overview of LENSES was designed with the aim to be readily available for printing by all project partners and to be shown in all national and international events organized both within and outside the project. The poster includes an introductory session “From Nexus thinking to Nexus doing” and 5 further sessions that explain, respectively, the 4 Nexus domains, the 9 specific project objectives, the 7 pilot areas, the 8 methodological approaches adopted and the type of stakeholders (i.e. public, private, multilateral) addressed by the project. In addition, this poster includes details on the project, such as Duration, Total Budget and EU contribution.

Figure 9: LENSES general poster

4.4 LENSES roll-up

Based upon the roll up template described in session 3.4 of this document, a project roll-up including an overview on LENSES was designed with the aim to be readily available for printing by all project partners and to be shown in all national and international event organized both within and outside the project. The roll up includes an introductory session “From Nexus thinking to Nexus doing” and 5 further sessions that explain, respectively, the 4 Nexus domains, the 9 specific project objectives, the 7 pilot areas, the 8 methodological approaches adopted and the type of stakeholders (i.e. public, private, multilateral) addressed within the project.

the LENSES project

LEarning and action alliances for Nexus Environments in an uncertain future

LENSES

CONSORTIUM

- Coordinated by **crea** (Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria)
- TESAF** (Technical University of Sofia)
- ISA** (International Science and Technology Center)
- cit|e|o|r** (Center for Integrated and Transdisciplinary Research)
- agriSat** (Bioscience Resource Project)
- ecoadapt**
- SWRI** (Sustainable Water Resources Institute)
- TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF CRISTE**
- D.R.A.X.I.S.** (Distributed Research and Analysis in the Mediterranean)
- MIGAL** (Mediterranean Research Institute)
- YAPAD** (Youth and Policy in Agriculture and Rural Development)
- Ea-Tek** (European Association of Technical Experts)

FROM NEXUS THINKING TO NEXUS DOING

Moving beyond the scientific Nexus understanding, LENSES aims to support the operationalization of the Nexus paradigm (from Nexus thinking to Nexus doing), therefore contributing to improve water allocation, enhance food security while preserving ecosystems and aiding climate change adaptation.

LENSES integrates the concepts of sustainable Nexus management with a resilience-oriented approach, leading stakeholders in accepting uncertainty as integral part of management and decision-making processes.

NEXUS DOMAINS

LENSES will enable multi-stakeholders communities to move from domain thinking to Nexus Thinking and Nexus Doing in very practical ways. It will enhance the understanding of the complex web of interactions affecting the nexus by using algorithms which link the different domains and run dynamic scenarios. Vulnerabilities across the nexus domains will be reduced by harnessing ecosystem services and biodiversity through e.g. nature-based solutions.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. To identify Nexus Domain Objectives (DOs) & Nexus Resilience Qualities (NRQ) that facilitate the transition.
2. To activate Learning & Action Alliances (LAAAs) to drive the Nexus dialogue.
3. To develop Participatory System Dynamics Models (PSDM) to support evidence-based policy design.
4. To co-design scenarios to test WEF Nexus resilience.
5. To carry out Ecosystem Services (ES) assessments to inform multi-objective policies and measures.
6. To assess and manage interdependencies between Nexus and SDGs.
7. To improve Natural Governance and align WEF policies toward Nexus management.
8. To build Nexus business cases using environmental and ecological economics.
9. To plan Nature-based Solutions (NBS) measures to co-achieve multiple DOs.

PILOT AREAS

All selected pilot areas represent typical Mediterranean conditions, at the same time being very heterogeneous for their focus on conflicting water and land uses, food production chains, farmland, forest and natural ecosystems conservation activities, co-existence of agriculture, and other (e.g. tourism, industrial production, etc.) productive realms. Specific lessons from the pilots will be captured to capitalize in the future elsewhere in similar environments.

MULTIPLE STAKEHOLDERS

LENSES will support a mutual-learning process in multi-stakeholder communities among the pilots. This will help identify existing WEF challenges and conflicts in resource uses, assess the multi-dimensional implications of choices and policies and exploring pathways to implementing specific measures (e.g. nature-based solutions).

PUBLIC
Public Authorities & Policy Makers; National Universities & Research Institutes; Asset Owners; River Basin/ Water Management bodies; Media & press (local, national, EU & Med).

PRIVATE
Farmers; Cooperatives; NGOs & CBOs; Water Users Associations; Relevant Associations; Participants in LAAAs & general public.

MULTILATERAL
International Organizations & Processes; International Financial Institutions & Donors; Multinational Research Centers.

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

LENSES follows a mixed methodology. On one hand, it is guided by hypothesis and the need for generalizable findings and broadly applicable methodologies and, on the other hand, by the need for a challenge-driven innovation approach. Here below, a list of LENSES key approaches.

- Participatory Approaches and Learning & Action Alliances (LAAAs)
- Policy Recommendations
- Participatory System Dynamics Modelling (PSDM)
- Ecosystem Services Assessments
- Nexus-SDG co-evaluations
- Natural Resource Economics
- Nature-based Solutions
- Gender dimension

COORDINATOR
www.leneses-prima.eu
info.leneses@crea.gov.it

PILOT
Duration: 01 May 2021 - 30 April 2024
Budget: 1,000,000,000
PR project number: 2198-2020-20

PRIMA IN THE MEDITERRANEAN AREA

This roll-up reflects only the author's view and the PRIMA Foundation is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This project is part of the PRIMA programme supported by the European Union. doi: 10.1016/j.ijer.2021.100120 (Section 1 Nexus IA)

Figure 10: LENSES general roll-up

4.5 LENSES Website

A dedicated project website (<http://www.lenses-prima.eu>) has been developed in October 2021 (M6) and is updated on a regular basis. It will remain available online for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

The website is the first source of information about the project, therefore it contains the right information in a clear and accessible design and structure ². It is written in a simple language and uses clear messages that can be understood by a broad target audience. The contents of the website have been organized in a way that keywords can be easily found.

The graphic layout of the website is consistent with the LENSES visual identity and includes all elements required to comply with the general rules for communication and dissemination activities of projects financed under the PRIMA Foundation programme.

The upper frame of the website includes: the project title and the link to the main LENSES social channels (i.e. Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn), and the logo of the project, the search function and the website menu bar. The menu bar gives access to 9 main web sections: Home; Summary; Pilot areas; Methodology; Outcomes; Events; Partners; Contacts and Partner area. The last page is accessible only upon registration, by members of the project *consortium*.

The LENSES website homepage, its structure and its main contents are represented in Figure 11 and described in the following paragraph.

Figure 11: Structure of the LENSES website homepage

² Pinnacle, *Project Communication Guide*, INTERREG VIC Programme, April 2012, p. 13.

The left frame of the homepage includes the logo and the link to the Contracting Authority website (<https://prima-med.org/>) and the EU emblem logo that embeds the link to EU website (https://ec.europa.eu/info/index_en). The left frame includes the logo and the link to the website of the leading partner institution (<https://www.crea.gov.it/>).

Among all the different web sections, the webpage dedicated to the [Outcomes](#) of the project is of particular interest. In fact, it includes access to the following contents:

- the 2 main platforms developed in the framework of LENSES: The Learning and Action Alliances (LAAs) and the Catalogue of Nature Based Solutions;
- repository of public deliverables; and
- repository of common communication and dissemination tools to be used during project-related meetings and workshops (e.g. posters, brochures).

The [Summary](#) section gives an overview of the project including objectives, actors and geography, as well as expected results. Furthermore, it reports useful details on project funding through the table reported in Figure 12.

NAME OF THE ACTION AND ACRONYM	LEarning and action alliances for NexuS Environments in an uncertain future - LENSES
IMPLEMENTATION PERIOD	01 May 2021 – 30 April 2024 (36 months)
GRANT AGREEMENT N°	2041
FUNDED BY	The Partnership for Research and Innovation in the Mediterranean Area - The PRIMA Foundation
FUNDING PROGRAMME	The PRIMA programme supported by the European Union under the H2020 EU Funding for Research and Innovation - Call 2020 Section 1 Nexus IA
OVERALL BUDGET	EUR 3.482.000,00 (Three million four hundred eighty-two thousand euro)
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 2.998.000,00 (Two million nine hundred ninety-eight thousand euro)
COORDINATED BY	Council for Agricultural Research and Economics - CREA

The [Pilot areas](#) web section gives access to LENSES map from which various sub-sections dedicated to the 7 pilot areas can be accessed. The webpage dedicated to each pilot area includes the logo of the institution responsible for the pilot area, which embeds the link to partner institution webpage within the LENSES website. At the bottom of the partner institution logo, the name of the pilot area leader is reported. On the left side, the website page gives access to the section “Pilot related documents” which includes the Pilot area factsheet and other dedicated C&D products developed in the framework of the project activities.

Figure 12: LENSES funding details

The “[partner area](#)” section is accessible only by members of the project, upon registration. It includes access to four sub-

sections:

- Templates, which includes editable version of all C&D tools;
- Meeting documents (e.g. PPT presentations used during the plenary meetings);
- Confidential deliverables; and
- Press kit.

The “[Events](#)” section contains details and links on past and future events developed both within and outside the project and focusing on LENSES related topics. For each project event, a specific webpage has been created and is being updated continuously on the website.

The “[Partner](#)” section gives access to various webpages, each one of it dedicated to one of the thirteen partner institutions. Every webpage dedicated to a partner institution includes:

- the logo and the link to the homepage of the website of the partner institution;
- a link to access a repository of press releases launched by each partner institution at national level;

- details on all team members involved in the project activities. For each team member the webpage reports: a recent picture, a short biography and the role(s) covered in the LENSES project.

4.6 Social channels

a. LinkedIn

A LinkedIn account entitled “LENSES Prima” was created and is available via this [link](#). The LinkedIn profile page of LENSES includes an overview on the project and a link to the project website. The official LinkedIn account of the LENSES project will remain available online for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

b. YouTube

A YouTube account entitled “LENSES Prima” was created and is available via this [link](#). The YouTube page of LENSES includes all videos developed in the context of Task 9.5 “Story as a driver of change”. The official YouTube account of the LENSES project will remain available online for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

c. Twitter

A Twitter account entitled “The LENSES Project” was created and is available via this [link](#). The official Twitter account of the LENSES project will remain available online for at least 3 years after the completion of the project.

d. Facebook

Facebook assures a worldwide visibility. A Facebook page entitled “The LENSES Project” was created under the Facebook account of the Council for Agricultural Research and Economics (CREA) and is available via this [link](#). The official Facebook page of the LENSES project will remain available online for at least 3 years after the end of the project.

This Facebook page aims to transfer the LENSES knowledge to the general public and to raise the interest of a non-specialized audience towards LENSES-related topics.

4.7 Press kit

LENSES partners have prepared and keep updated a press kit including, e.g. a general project presentation, factsheets of the pilot areas, description of pilot activities, and biographies of key people participating in the project. Although press kits are designed for journalists, they can also be an important source of information for other people interested in the project – e.g. institutions, local governments, industry associations, regulatory bodies, governments, etc. Table 2 summarizes all the element of which the press kit is composed and, on its right column, provides the link to access each specific element.

Table 2: Communication products included in the LENSES press kit

Type of template/document	Type of product (Ready for the public/template for internal use)	Link where to find the template/document
General products (i.e. poster, brochure, PPT) about the project: what is LENSES doing and why is it interesting?	Ready for the public	https://www.lenses-prima.eu/outcomes/communication-and-dissemination/
A template for press releases	Template for internal use	https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partner-area/templates/
Any brochure or materials that might be interesting for journalists.	Ready for the public	https://www.lenses-prima.eu/outcomes/communication-and-dissemination/
Pilot factsheet (1 per pilot area)	Ready for the public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Pinios 2- Koiliaris critical zone 3- Gediz 4- Tarquinia plain 5- Doñana region 6- Hula Valley 7- Deir Alla
Relevant recent articles published about the project	Ready for the public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- https://www.lenses-prima.eu/outcomes/communication-and-dissemination/ ; and 2- “Press release” area available in the web section dedicated to each partner institution (e.g. for CREA visit: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/crea_team/crea-press-release/).
Recent press releases	Ready for the public	“Press release” area available in the web section dedicated to each partner institution (e.g. for CREA visit: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/crea_team/crea-press-release/).
Biographies of each team member involved	Ready for the public	Available in the web section dedicated to each partner institution. For instance,

in LENSES and its role in the project		for CREA visit: https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partners/crea_team/)
Recent photos of the project events.	Ready for the public (1) or files available for internal use (2)	1- https://www.lenses-prima.eu/events/ 2- https://www.lenses-prima.eu/partner-area/meeting-documents/

a. Template for press releases

To support the work of the partners to build and keep alive relationships with the media, a template for press releases has been prepared and made available to all partners in the “Template” folder created within the Partner Area of the project website, accessible upon registration (it can be accessed via this [link](#)). The press release template includes all graphic elements characterizing both the project and the PRIMA foundation and is presented in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Template for press release including all mandatory elements defined by the GA.

5. Final remarks

The aim of the present deliverable 9.2 “Visual identity and project identity material” is to give a detailed overview on the various visual tools created in order to ensure an effective and well-structured dissemination and following exploitation of the LENSES project. Additionally, it helps the LENSES partners to properly use these visual identity materials and to consequently achieve a professional and sophisticated visual appearance of LENSES. The visual identity and communication materials (e.g. the brochure, the roll-up and

the website) follow a coherent logic, aiming at raising awareness on the WEF Nexus and the interactions among the four domains (water allocation, ecosystem services, food production, climate adaptation) and their impacts, in a cross-cutting manner; and facilitating a **shift from Nexus Thinking to Resilient Nexus Doing** to strengthen resilience and unlock the potential to create new socio-economic opportunities.

Leaving behind the complication often associated with science, the project's visual identity aims to make the symbiosis and interactions among the four domains of the Nexus more accessible to the general public and consequently to the user of the results and products emerging from the project. By developing a professional joint image and appearance, a sound basis for further dissemination and exploitation activities has been set.

A preliminary version of the present deliverable "Visual identity and project identity material" was released in M6. Thereafter, the document has been updated, thanks to the contributions of all project partners, until the release of this final version, which occurs in October 2022 (M18).

The present "Visual identity and project identity material" deliverable has been built by taking into account the instructions shared by the PRIMA Foundation Project Officer in the context of the LENSES kick-off meeting.

6. References

LENSES Grant Agreement

LENSES Consortium Agreement between the CREA and the LENSES partners

D9.1 LENSES Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Pinnacle, "Project Communication Guide – INTERREG IVC Programme", 2012 release

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